

An optimized protocol for the extraction, purification and stabilization of RNA from challenging fungi

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1. INTRODUCTION

Proper extraction of RNA from fungi is essential for various molecular biology applications aimed at understanding their genetic and functional dynamics. In addition, RNA-seq data provides robust prediction of gene models in novel genomes (Gabriel et al., 2023). However, fungal biomass presents challenges due to its robust cell wall structure and endogenous RNase activity (Leite et al, 2012). Conventional phenol-chloroform extraction, while cost-effective and yielding high RNA, can result in contamination that impacts downstream applications (Sakya et al, 2023).

To address these challenges, a modified protocol utilizing TRIzol™ reagent is introduced, ensuring efficient RNA extraction while minimizing contamination and preserving RNA integrity. The protocol begins with sample preparation, including fungal cultivation and lyophilization, followed by RNA extraction using TRIzol™ reagent. Throughout the extraction process, precautions are taken to eliminate nucleases and ensure RNA integrity. Subsequent steps involve RNA purification using specialized kits, further enhancing RNA quality, and removing contaminants. Finally, methods for solubilization and preservation of RNA are outlined, providing guidelines for long-term storage.

2. FIELD OF APPLICATION

Applications of RNA samples from fungi are diverse and impactful across various fields such as gene expression studies, pathogen research, RNA sequencing (RNA-seq), functional genomics, biotechnology applications, evolutionary biology, and environmental research. Depending on the downstream application, elution volumes and concentration requirements may vary.

3. MATERIALS AND REAGENTS LIST FOR RNA EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION PROTOCOL

- **Sample Preparation:**
 - Preferred fungal media (e.g., MEA)
 - Vacuum filter funnel and filter paper (or centrifuge)
 - Distilled water
 - 75% ethanol
 - Lyophilizer
 - Mortar and pestle
 - 5 ml Eppendorf tubes
- **RNA Extraction using TRIzol™:**
 - TRIzol™ reagent (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific)
 - RNaseZap™ RNase decontamination solution (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific)
 - Liquid nitrogen
 - Chloroform
 - Isopropanol
 - Parafilm
 - RNase-free water
- **RNA Purification**
 - PureLink RNA Mini Kit (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific)
 - 70% ethanol
 - RNase-Free Water
 - RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 Kit (Zymo Research) (for further purification step)
- **DNase Treatment:**

- TURBO DNA-free™ Kit (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific)
- **Stabilization and Preservation of RNA:**
 - 3M NaOAc solution (pH 5.2)
 - 100% ethanol
 - DEPC water
- **Additional Equipment:**
 - Centrifuge
 - Vortex
 - Heat block or incubator
 - Water bath
 - NanoDrop One (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
 - Bioanalyzer or Tape Station with RNA nano kits (Agilent)

Hints: Ensure all solutions are RNase-free or treated with DEPC. Maintain all steps involving RNA at cold temperatures (on ice) to preserve RNA integrity. Following manufacturer protocols for all kits used is essential for successful RNA extraction, purification, and stabilization.

4. PROTOCOL

4.1. Sample preparation

1. Cultivate fungi in the preferred media (e.g., inoculate on MEA for 7-14 days, depending on the strain) until they reach the mid-exponential phase. For fungi that produce high amount of conidia, which usually are highly pigmented, biomass should be picked before conidiation, if possible.
2. Filter the fungi through a vacuum filter funnel and filter paper. Alternatively, centrifuge the fungal samples, wash them with distilled water three times, and then obtain a tight fungal pellet, removing all liquid from the tube. Subsequently, store the biomass at -80°C until lyophilization.
3. Lyophilize the resulting biomass for 24-58 hours.

4.2. RNA extraction using Trizol

At this stage, TRIzol™ reagent (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher) is utilized, and the manufacturer's instructions are followed with some modifications:

Use RNaseZap™ RNase for decontamination and elimination RNAasy from working space or prepare a decontaminating mixture consisting of 10% (vol/vol) sodium hypochlorite, 1% (wt/vol) sodium dodecyl sulfate, 1% (wt/vol) sodium hydroxide (NaOH), 1% (wt/vol) sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) (Fischer et al., 2016). Ethanol and 2-propanol can also inhibit nuclease activity but evaporate quickly.

1. Weight ≈ 0.15 grams of lyophilized biomass.
2. Thoroughly grind the dried biomass with liquid nitrogen using a mortar and pestle until it becomes a ground powder.

Hint: Use a mortar and pestle that has been at -80°C for 5 minutes before extraction to improve grinding.

3. Transfer the ground biomass to a 5 ml Eppendorf tube and add 1 ml of cold TRIzol™ reagent (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific). Seal the tube tightly with parafilm around the screw cap.

Hint 1: Alternatively, TRIzol™ can be added directly to the ground biomass inside the mortar. With the addition of liquid nitrogen, grind it until reaching a consistency resembling ice cream. Then, transfer the samples into Eppendorf tubes.

Hint 2: Using a sterilized silicon spatula facilitates the collection of the sample from the mortar and its transfer to an Eppendorf tube.

Hint 3: Perform all subsequent steps on ice.

4. Centrifuge the lysate at 12,000 ×g for 5 min at 10 °C.
5. Incubate the supernatant in new Eppendorf for 5 min.
6. Add 0.2 mL of chloroform per 1 mL TRIzol and incubate for 2-3 minutes.
7. Centrifuge the samples for 15 minutes at 12,000 ×g at 4 °C.
8. Transfer the colorless upper aqueous phase containing the RNA to a new tube.
9. Add 0.5 mL of Isopropanol to the aqueous phase and incubate for 10 minutes.
10. Centrifuge for 10 minutes at 12,000 ×g at 4 °C.
11. Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 1 ml of 75% ethanol. Vortex the sample, then centrifuge for 5 minutes at 7500 ×g at 4°C. If RNA purification is desired, proceed directly to the section “4.3 RNA purification with PureLink RNA Mini Kit”, step 2.
12. Remove the supernatant and air dry or vacuum dry the RNA pellet for 5 minutes.
13. Resuspend the pellet in 50 µl of RNAase-free water by pipetting up and down. Measure sample concentration with NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and check RNA integrity with TapeStation (Agilent) or equivalent. The RNA Integrity Number (RIN) should be ≥ 8 for sequencing applications. If RNA concentration is low, proceed directly with the section “4.5, Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research)”.

Hint: To aid dissolution, incubate in a water bath at 55°C for 10 minutes. Alternatively, vortex thoroughly and leave the sample on ice for 1 minute after each vortexing step.

4.3. RNA purification with PureLink RNA Mini Kit (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific)

This optional step is particularly suitable in cases of poor 260/230 or 260/280 Nanodrop ratios. Follow the kit protocol for the Purification RNA PureLink RNA Mini Kit (Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher).

a) To purify RNA follow these steps:

These steps guarantee the effective purification of RNA, eliminating contaminants while preserving its integrity for subsequent applications.

1. Add 1 volume of 70% ethanol to eluted RNA in the RNase-free tube.
2. Vortex the tube to mix thoroughly and disperse any visible precipitate that may form after adding ethanol.
3. Transfer up to 700 µL of the sample, including any remaining precipitate, to the Spin Cartridge along with the Collection Tube.

4. Centrifuge the Spin Cartridge at $12,000 \times g$ for 15 seconds at room temperature. Discard the flow-through and reinsert the Spin Cartridge into the same Collection Tube.

5. Repeat steps 3-4 until the entire sample has been processed.

b) Column Washing

1. Add 700 μL of Wash Buffer I to the Spin Cartridge.

2. Centrifuge the Spin Cartridge at $12,000 \times g$ for 15 seconds at room temperature.

3. Discard both the flow-through and the Collection Tube. Place the Spin Cartridge into a new Collection Tube.

4. Add 500 μL of Wash Buffer II with ethanol to the Spin Cartridge.

5. Centrifuge the Spin Cartridge at $12,000 \times g$ for 15 seconds at room temperature.

6. Discard the flow-through and reinsert the Spin Cartridge into the same Collection Tube.

7. Repeat steps 4-6 one more time for thorough purification.

c) RNA elution

1. Centrifuge the Spin Cartridge with Collection Tube at $12,000 \times g$ for 1 min at room temperature.

2. Discard the Collection Tube and insert the Spin Cartridge into a Recovery Tube.

3. Add 30 μL to 100 μL RNase-Free Water to the center of the Spin.

4. Incubate at room temperature for 1 min.

5. Centrifuge at $12,000 \times g$ for 2 min at room temperature

6. Measure sample concentration with NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and check RNA integrity with TapeStation (Agilent) or equivalent. The RNA Integrity Number (RIN) should be ≥ 8 for sequencing applications. If RNA concentration is low, proceed directly with the section “4.5. Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research)”.

4.4. DNase treatment

The TURBO DNA-free™ Kit from Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific is used. This step is optional depending on the downstream application. For RNA-seq, DNase treatment is strongly recommended, while it is mandatory for real-time qPCR. The standard reaction volume is 50 μL , with possible volumes ranging from 10 to 100 μL . Two tailored methods are available for DNase treatment, depending on the level of DNA contamination and the nucleic acid concentration in the sample.

Routine DNase Treatment

- **Sample Condition:** Sample contains $\leq 200 \mu\text{g}$ nucleic acid per mL.

1. Add 0.1 volume of 10X TURBO DNase™ Buffer and 1 μL of TURBO DNase™ Enzyme to the RNA sample. Mix gently.

2. Incubate at 37°C for 20–30 minutes.

3. Resuspend the DNase Inactivation Reagent by flicking or vortexing the tube before use.

4. Add 2 μL or 0.1 volume (whichever is greater) of resuspended DNase Inactivation Reagent to the RNA sample. Mix well.
5. Incubate for 5 minutes at room temperature, flicking the tube 2–3 times during the incubation to keep the DNase Inactivation Reagent suspended.
6. Centrifuge the samples at 10,000 $\times g$ for 1.5 minutes.
7. Carefully transfer the supernatant containing the RNA to a fresh tube, taking care not to disturb the DNase Inactivation Reagent pellet.

Rigorous DNase Treatment

- **Sample Condition:** Sample contains $>200 \mu\text{g}$ nucleic acid per mL or RNA that is severely contaminated with DNA (i.e., $>2 \mu\text{g}$ DNA/50 μL). These samples can be diluted prior to treatment, or if the sample cannot be diluted:

1. Dilute the RNA sample to 10 μg nucleic acid per 50 μL total volume if possible.
2. Add 0.1 volume of 10X TURBO DNase™ Buffer and the appropriate amount of TURBO DNase™ Enzyme (1 μL for diluted samples or 2–3 μL for undiluted samples). Mix gently.
3. Incubate at 37°C for 20–30 minutes. Optional: For enhanced DNase treatment, perform a two-step incubation by adding half the amount of TURBO DNase™ Enzyme initially, incubating at 37°C for 30 minutes, then adding the remaining half and continuing incubation for another 30 minutes.
4. Resuspend the DNase Inactivation Reagent by flicking or vortexing the tube before use.
5. Add 0.2 volumes of resuspended DNase Inactivation Reagent to the RNA sample. Mix well.
6. Incubate for 5 minutes at room temperature, flicking the tube 2–3 times during the incubation to keep the DNase Inactivation Reagent suspended.
7. Centrifuge the samples at 10,000 $\times g$ for 1.5 minutes.
8. Carefully transfer the supernatant containing the RNA to a fresh tube, taking care not to disturb the DNase Inactivation Reagent pellet
9. Measure sample concentration with NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and check RNA integrity with TapeStation (Agilent) or equivalent. The RNA Integrity Number (RIN) should be ≥ 8 for sequencing applications. If RNA concentration is low, proceed directly with the section “4.5. Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research)”.

Hint 1: Avoid introducing DNase Inactivation Reagent into solutions used for downstream enzymatic reactions as it can sequester divalent cations and alter buffer conditions.

Hint 2: Ensure the environment is maintained at room temperature (22–26°C) during incubation to facilitate proper DNase inactivation

4.5. Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research)

This optional step is particularly suitable for low concentrated samples, or in case of poor 260/230 or 260/280 Nanodrop ratios. This commercial kit allows to elute in as low as 6 μL , allowing increase concentration and maximum recovery for applications such as real time qPCR. RNA-seq samples will require larger elution volumes. Following the standard protocol, perform all steps at room temperature and centrifugation at 10,000–16,000 $\times g$ for 30 seconds, unless specified. To ensure DNA-free RNA (optional), perform DNase I treatment either before (recommended) or during the clean-up process.

1. Mix each sample with 2 volumes of RNA Binding Buffer. For example, combine 100 μL of buffer with 50 μL of sample.
2. Mix the sample with an equal volume of ethanol (95–100%). For instance, add 150 μL of ethanol.

3. Transfer the sample to the Zymo-Spin™ IICR Column in a collection tube and centrifuge, discarding the flow-through.
4. Apply 400 µl of RNA Prep Buffer to the column and centrifuge, discarding the flow-through.
5. Follow by adding 700 µl of RNA Wash Buffer to the column and centrifuge, discarding the flow-through.
6. Repeat the process by adding 400 µl of RNA Wash Buffer to the column and centrifuge for 1 minute to ensure complete removal of the wash buffer.
7. Finally, add 6-35 µl of DNase/RNase-Free Water directly to the column matrix and centrifuge.
8. Measure sample concentration with NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and check RNA integrity with TapeStation (Agilent) or equivalent. The RNA Integrity Number (RIN) should be ≥ 8 for sequencing applications. If RNA concentration is low, proceed directly with the section 4.5, Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research).

4.6. Further purification of RNA with RNA Clean & Concentrator™-25 kit (Zymo Research)

Protocol for RNA storage at RT:

After RNA extraction, perform DNase treatment (if required) according to Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific's protocol:

1. Prepare a 3M NaOAc solution. RNase-free or DEPC-H₂O must be used. pH must be adjusted to 5.2.
2. Add 0.1 volumes of 3M NaOAc (pH 5.2) to the post-DNase RNA sample.
3. Add 3 volumes of 100% ethanol (this calculation must consider the volume of sodium acetate; for example, for a 50 µl sample, 5 µl of sodium acetate and 165 µl of 100% ethanol is added)
4. To precipitate RNA: Centrifuge the samples at >13000 rpm for 30 minutes at 4 degrees (if samples are at room temperature, incubate them for 1 hour at -20 degrees)
5. Resuspend in 50 µl RNase-free- or DEPC-H₂O

Hint1: the protocol requires starting RNA samples with medium to high concentration and good integrity. It is recommended, the RNA concentration should be between 50-100 ng/µL to ensure successful outcomes.

Hint 2: starting with concentrations as low as 5-15 ng/µL may result in significant RNA loss. •Additionally, the initial RNA Integrity Number (RIN) should be in the range of 8.5-9.5 for optimal results.

Hint 3: in subsequent tests, RNA samples were left at room temperature on the bench for periods of 3 or 6 days

The integrity of RNA subjected to the above stabilization protocol was assessed by Tape Station (Agilent) immediately after extraction after 3 days at room temperature, and after 6 days at room temperature.

D1: 1598 T1

Sample Table

Well	RINe	28S/18S (Area)	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D1	9.5	1.4	44.3	1598 T1		

Fig 1. Sample measured immediately after extraction.

E1: 1598 T2

Sample Table

Well	RINe	28S/18S (Area)	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E1	8.8	1.1	50.8	1598 T2		

Fig 2. Sample measured after 3 days at room temperature.

FI: 1598 T3

Sample Table

Well	RINe	28S/18S (Area)	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
FI	8.6	1.6	28.9	1598 T3		

Fig 3. Sample measured after 6 days at room temperature.

Fig 4. Workflow of total RNA extraction from fungal biomass, using Trizol and commercial kits for purification.

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